

socijalno - andragoški - aspekti

ZNAČEVNOST NA SOCIJALNATA RABOTA VO OSTVARUVAVENATA OPŠTIVENATA GRUPOVA ZA LICATA SO INVALIDNOST

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 Sojuz na defektolozi na
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Rezime

Ostvaruvaveto na opštivenata grupa za licata so invalidnost e uslovena od stepenot na razvivenost na strukturnite slabosti za socijalna zaštita, angažiranost na medicinsките i defektološki kadri vo možne složeni proces na rehabilitacija i edukacija. Organite i slabite za socijalna zaštita i socijalna rabota, preku pravna regulativa se zadolženi da uestvuvaat vo obezbeduvawe, organizirawe i realizacija na opštivenata grupa za licata so invalidnost, proces koj potnuva od preventivata, otkrivaveto, dijagnostici raveto, rehabilitacijata, ostvaruvaveto na nivnite prava i trae do nivnoto vkluvuvawe, odnosno socijalna integracija kade što iverat i rabotata, a vo pogolem broj slučai i do krajot na nivnoto život.

Ključni zborovi: *socijalna rabota, opštivenata grupa, licata so invalidnost, deca so posebni obrazovni potrebi, etički aspekti i socijalna integracija*

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social and adult aspects

IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL WORK IN IMPLEMENTATION OF SOCIAL CARE FOR DISABLED PEOPLE

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Abstract

The implementation of social care for disabled people is conditioned by the level of development of the professional services for social care, engagement of medical and special education staff in a very complex process of rehabilitation and education. The organs and services of social care and social work, through legal regulations, are obliged to participate in providing, organization and implementation of social care for disabled people. This process starts with prevention, detection, diagnosis, rehabilitation, realization of their rights and lasts until their inclusion, i.e. social integration and in a large number of cases to the end of their lives.

Key words: *social work, social care, disabled people, children with special education needs, ethical aspects and social integration*

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Voved

^ovekot kako individua se ra|a donesu-
vaj}i so sebe na ovoj svet ogromna "bov~a#
svoe biogenetsko poteklo i socijalno
milje i toa vo mo{ ne raznoliko, krajno
slo`eno i neizvesno semejno i op{ testve-
no opkru`uvawe, taka da nezavisno od svo-
jot vrednosni sistem, ni semejstvoto, ni
op{ testvoto vo kontekst na ni vni ot mate-
rijalen i duhoven razvoj ne se vo mo`nost
bez posebno organizirani i nsticiional-
ni aktivnosti da obezbedat uslovi za so-
cijalizacija na ~ovekovata edinka. Toa
dotolku pove}e koga se vo pra{awe lica
so invalidnost, { to ne smee da se tretira
kako "nus proizvod# na biolo{kite, soci-
jalnite, ekonomskite, ekolo{kite i drugi
procesi svrzani so ~ovekovata egzisten-
cija, bidej}i istoriski e verificirana
aksiomata deka toa e del od negovot en-
titet i celokupnoto bitisuvawe. Zatoa
misijata na socijalnata rabota vo huma-
nizacija na uslovi te za `ivot, odnosno na
licata so invalidnost, e dlaboko ~oveki
determinirana nu`nost na op{ testvenata
praktika, osobeno vo oblata na socijal-
nata za{tita i socijalnata politika vo
sekoe civilizirano op{ testvo.

Su{tinata na socijalno-za{titi ot tret-
man e opredelena od slo`enosta i speci-
fiki~nosta na etiolo{kite faktori i te-
`inata na ni vni te posledi ci koi ostavaat
{iroka lepeza na heterogeni potrebi vo
kontekstot na razli~ni stepeni i vi dovi
psihosomatski o{tetuvawa na populacija-
ta. Logi~no e deka licata so invalidnost,
{to pretstavuvaat slo`ena struktura i m-
perativno nametnuva diferencirani i in-
terdisciplinaren tretman, od aspekt na
socijalnata za{tita, medicinata, defek-
tologijata, pedagogijata, psihologijata i
drugite nau~ni podra~ja i disciplini.

Napori te na organizirane, slu`bite, organi-
zacii te i ustanovite mora da bidat naso-
~eni kon koristewe sovremeni stru~ni i
nau~ni iskustva za pokvaliteten `ivot,
gradewe konzistenten sistem na za{tita

Introduction

The human beings are born with "basket" full of
their own biogenetic origin and social milieu in
very heterogeneous, complex and uncertain
family and social environment and regardless
their value system, neither family nor the soci-
ety in the context of their material and spiritual
development are able, without specially organ-
ized institutional activities, to provide condi-
tions for socialization of human beings. When
disabled people are in question, they must not
be treated as "side effect" of biological, social,
economic, ecological or other processes con-
nected with human existence, since the histori-
cally verified axiom is that is a part of human
entity and existence. Therefore, the mission of
social work in humanization of life conditions,
i.e. disabled people, is deep human determined
necessity of social practice, especially in social
care and social policy of a civilized society.

The essence of social care treatment is deter-
mined by the complexity and specifics of etio-
logical factors and weight of their consequences
with wide range of heterogenic needs in the
context of different levels and types of psycho-
somatic impairments of population. People with
disabilities are a complex structure and they
imperatively impose differentiated and interdis-
ciplinary treatment from the aspect of social
care, medicine, special education and rehabilita-
tion, pedagogy, psychology and other scientific
areas and disciplines.

The efforts of organs, services, organizations
and institutions must be directed towards use of
contemporary professional and scientific ex-
periences for better quality life, building up
consistent system of care

i rehabilitacija { to } e ovozmo`i koordinirano ostvaruvawe na vrednosnite opredelbi na op{ testvoto vo odnosot kon licata so invalidnost. Organite i slu`bite za socijalna za{tita, odnosno socijalna rabota, dolgotrajno i naglaseno u-estvuvaat vo obezbeduvawe, organizirawe i realizirawe na za{tita, tretman, socijalna integracija, kako proces koj po-uvuwa od preventiva, otkrivawe, dijagnostici rawe, rehabilitacija, ostvaruvawe na ni vni te prava i trae do ni vno vkl u-uvawe vo op{ testveni ot`ivot, a vo poedini slu`ai i do ni vnata smrt. Nema da zgre{ime ako potenci rame deka socijalnata rabota izrazena preku organite i slu`bite, a posebno preku dejnostite na centrite za socijalna rabota vo ostvaruvaweto na op{ testvenata gri`a za licata so invalidnost, pretstavuva **sostojba bez koja ne se mo`e** zaradi ni vnata egzistencija, odnosno za{tita i rehabilitacija. Toa nedvosni sleno go potvrduva faktot za soznani eto deka "predmetot na socijalnata rabota e sevkupnata `ivotna situacija na ~ovekot vo op{ testvoto, celokupnosta na socijalni te, ekonomski te, biolo{ki te, psiholo{ki te i fizi~ki te uslovi imaj}i vo predvidni vnoto vlijani e vrz`ivotot, zadovoluvaweto na osnovni te `ivotni potrebi i socijalna komunikacija, t.e. funkcioni raweto na poedinecot, semejstvoto i op{ testveni te grupi #.

1. Nekoi od pretpostavit e za izbor na socijalna rabota kako profesija povrzana so op{ testvenata gri`a na licata so invalidnost

Op{ testvenata gri`a na licata so invalidnost, ima po{iroka op{ testvena dimenzija otkolku { to se misli i deluva vo praktikata. Problemi gi ti{tat ne samo niv sami te, tuku i ni vni te semejstva, rodini, prijатели i op{ testvoto so svoite insti tucii. Se pretpostavuva deka 30% od populacijata neposredno e vrzana so problemi te na ovi e licai ni vnata sudbina.

and rehabilitation, which will enable coordinated realization of social value determination in regard with disabled people. Organs and services of social care, i.e. social work, participate in providing, organization and implementation of care, treatment, social integration as a process that starts with prevention, detection, diagnosis, rehabilitation, realization of their rights and lasts until their inclusion in social life and in some cases to the end of their lives. Social work is expressed through organs and services, especially through centers for social work in realization of social care for disabled people and is *conditio sine kua non* of their existence, i.e. care and rehabilitation. This is proved by the fact that "the objectives of social work are entire human lives in society, their social, economic, biological, psychological and physical conditions, having in mind their influence on life, satisfaction of basic human needs and social communication, i.e. functioning of the individual, family and social groups".

1. Some hypotheses on choosing social work as profession connected to social care of disabled people

Social care of disabled people has a wider social dimension than it is considered in practice. These problems are not only theirs, but they refer to their families, relatives, friends and society with its institutions. It is assumed that 30% of the population is directly connected to the problems of these people and their destinies.

Tokmu poradi toa, prioritete vo op{ testveno-humane osnovi na razvojot na institucionalnata za{tita na vakvite lica, ne smeata da gubat od svoeto znaewe, osobeno koga se vo praawe ekonomskite determinanti vo sega{nive uslovi na tranzicija na op{testvoto. Vo taasmi sl odat vo priloge analizi i soznani ja kako:

- Visokot procent na licata so invalidnost vo vкупnata populacija na naselenieto (koja spored podatoci na OON iznesuva 10%) kriee znaaen raboten potencial {to bi останал nedovolno ili voop{to neiskoristen, ako ne se obezbedat uslovi za nivna rehabilitacija, odnosno rabotno-profesionalno osposobuvawe i postojano birastele potrebite od golemi materijalni izdatoci za nivno socijalno obezbeduvawe i zdravstvena za{tita.

- Se pravat ogromni materijalni zagubi zaradi preokupiranost na lenovite na semejstvoto okolu gr`ata za licata so invalidnost izrazeni preku namalena produktivnost, otsustvo od rabota, naru{uvawe na zdravjeto, povredi pri rabota, naru{uvawe na semejnata ramnote`a, oddavawe na asocijalni pojavi i mnogu drugo. Za op{testvenata i ekonomskata dimenzija na tretmanot na licata so invalidnost nu`ni se seopfatni interdisciplinarni nau-ni istra`uvawa.

^ovekot so invalidnost eslo`ena struktura koja mora da se gleda kako splet od nizafaktori (biolo{ki, socijalni, psiholo{ki, edukativni, ekonomski, etiki i dr.) ~ievlijane ne mo`e da se predvidi izatoa se potrebni anga`mani od stru~nikadri vo nivniot interdisciplinaren tretman, od op{testveni organi, organizacii, institucii od oblastana zdravstvoto, socijalnata za{tita, trudot i dr.

Otsustvoto na koordinacija me|uzainterresiranite ~initeli vo zaedni~koto re{avawe na problemite na licata so invalidnost vodi kon **marginalizacija na problemite, vo improvizirawe i minimi-**

That is why the priorities of social and human basis of institutionalized care development of such people must not lose their meaning especially when the economic determinants in the present conditions of transitional society are in question. There are many analysis and knowledge related to this:

- The high percentage of disabled people out of total population (according to UN data is 10%) hides a significant work potential, which would stay unused if conditions for their rehabilitation, i.e. work and professional training were not provided. The needs for large material expenses for their social and health care would continuously rise.

- Large material losses are made, due to preoccupation of family members for care of disabled people expressed through reduced productivity, absence from work, health disturbances, work injuries, family balance disturbance, different asocial appearances etc. Comprehensive interdisciplinary scientific researches on social and economic dimension of disabled people treatment are necessary. The disabled people are complex structures that must be treated as a mixture of number of factors (biological, social, psychological, education, economic, ethical etc.) which influence cannot be anticipated and engagements of professional staff in their interdisciplinary treatment, social organs, organizations, institutions in the field of health and social care, labor etc are needed.

The absence of coordination among interested factors in solving the problems of disabled people leads to **marginalization of problems, improvisation and minimization of activities**

ziranje na dejnostite vo kreiranje sistemski rešenja, strukturna interpretacija i postojna praksa

Menuvaweto na op{testveni odnos konlicata so invalidnost bara organizirana rabota od dr`avni te institucii, socialno-humanitarnite organizacii i dobrovolni nevladini organizacii zaradi informirawe na javnosta za problemite i podgotovkite na `ivotnite i rabotnite sredini za nivno prifa}awe i socialna integracija.

1.1. Specifi~nite potrebi na licata so invalidnost kako osnova za organizirawe i kreiranje socialna rabota

Specifi~nite potrebi {to ja karakteriziraat `ivotnata egzistencija na licata popre~eni vo psihofizi~kiot razvoj se manifestiraat vo {irok dijapazon usloven od vid i stepenot na o{tetenosta kako posledica na etiolo{ki faktori. Nivna celosna identifikacija, nivno voop{tuvawe i stavawe pod zaedni~ki imenitel prakti~no e nevozmo`no. Je spomneme potrebi vrzani za odredeni o{tetuvawa, kako {to se gubewe vid, sluh, mentalna retardacija, telesna invalidnost. Socialnite rabotnici vo Centrite za socialna rabota i vo socialno humanitarnite organizacii treba da znaat da komuniciraat so licata so invalidnost na soodveten na~in vo nivnite brojni `ivotni situacii. Toa se oblici na pomo{zavisni od specifi~nite potrebi usloveni od psihosomatskite o{tetuvawa {to baraat anga`man na socialni rabotnici vo kontekstot na nivnata profesionalna i etika kompetencija.

O{tetuvawata na organot za vid i nepravatna funkcija ostava te{ki posledici {to se reflektiraat vrz formirawe na li~nosta, osposobuvawe za rabota i sevkupni ot`ivot, nametnuvaj}i problemi od socialna, edukativna, psiholo{ka i ekonomska priroda.

in creating systemic solutions, professional interpretation and existing practice.

Changing social relation towards disabled people requires organized work of state institutions, social and humanitarian organizations and charity non-governmental organizations in order to inform public about the problems and preparations of life and work environments for their acceptance and social integration.

1.1. Specific needs of disabled people as a base for organizing and creating social work

Specific needs, which characterize life existence of people with psychophysical developmental disabilities, are manifested in a wide range conditioned by the type and level of the impairment as result of etiological factors. Their complete identification, their generalization and putting them under common denominator, practically is impossible. We shall mention some needs related to certain impairments, such as vision loss, hearing, mental retardation, physical disabilities. Social workers of centers for social work and social and humanitarian organizations should know how to communicate with disabled people in a number of their life situations. Those are forms of assistance, depending on the specific needs and conditioned by psychosomatic impairments that require engagement of social workers in the context of their professional and ethical competence.

Vision organ impairments and its function

leave severe consequences that are reflected on formation of personality, training for work and life, imposing problems of social, educational, psychological and economic nature

Struktura vidne sposobnosti je proces usloven od faktorija, koja su međusobno povezana i imaju važnu ulogu za integritet kao individualno i opće testveno bitie u svakodnevnoj praksi i komunikaciji.

Općenito gledano, treba se gledati dva aspekta: kao kriterij za koristi i kao kriterij za stvaranje uslova za integraciju u opće testveno bitie na osnovu sposobnosti za samostalni život.

Osnovni problemi ljudi su izgubljena orijentacija i kretanje u prostoru, problemi u pisanju i čitanju. Od ovih problema proizlaze i specifične biosocijalne potrebe, odnosno potreba za igrom, druženjem, priznavanjem od društva (grupna, kolektivna, obiteljna zajednica), potreba za savremenim informacijskim sredstvima-kompjuteri i osposobljavanje za njihovu korištenje.

Od stupnja uspjeha ovisi o tome na koje specifične probleme, koje zavisi i socijalna integracija na ovim ljudima. To je usloveno od mnogih faktora: etiologija i dob, vrijeme na početku organiziranog tretmana, koordinacija i povezanost na socijalna, tjelesna i psihološka komponenta tretmana, kulturno-obrazovni i socijalni status u obitelji, bližnja sredina, opremanost na institucije koje se bave rehabilitacijom, organizacija na radnom mjestu u ustanovi za podugoročno zadržavanje, stručnost i kvalifikacije kadrova i stavovi na radnom mjestu i u društvu.

Nivo socijalne integracije ljudi ovisi o prirodi i težini bolesti, koja dovodi do općeg slabljenja (razni zaboljavanja, nasljedni faktori, traumi i dr.), što ima posljedice za sposobnost fizičku, psihičku i socijalnu komponentu.

The structure of people with impaired vision is a process conditioned by factors, which are mutually connected and have crucial importance for their integrity as individuals and social beings in everyday practical communication.

Vision impairments can be seen through two aspects: as a criterion for benefits and rights of these people established by the social community according to the principles of humanism and solidarity and a criterion for creating conditions for integration in society on the basis of training for individual life.

The basic problems of people with lost vision are orientation and movement in space, problems of alphabet and writing. Out of these problems, specific biosocial needs emerge, i.e. need for play, friendship, society recognition (group, collective, family community), needs for contemporary information means – computers and training for their use.

Social integration of these people will depend on the level of successful solving of specific problems. That is conditioned by many factors, such as etiology and age, beginning of organized treatment; coordination and connection of social, teflo-pedagogical and psychological components of treatment. Then, cultural and educational and social status of the family; closer environment, equipment of the institutions for rehabilitation; organization of work in dispensary institutions for longer stay of these people; professionalism of employed staff and attitudes of public towards blind people.

Level of social integration of people with impaired hearing depends on the nature and reasons for the impairments (different diseases, innate factors, traumas etc.) with consequences for people with physical, psychic and social component.

@i votot na ~ovekot se odvi va vrz postavu- vawe vrski { to zavisa od komunikacija i odnose so lu|eto i socijalna sredi na. Celokupnata komunikacija na ~ovekot kako op{ testveno bitie ja ostvaruva preku govorot. Kaj gluvite lica zaradi zagubeni ot sluh mu e onevozm`eno spontano u~ewe na govorot, se javuvaat slo`eni problemi vo procesot na ni vnoto ospobuwawe i socijalizacija. Treba da se prezemat merki i aktivnosti za ubla`u vawe i kompenzirawe na posledici te od zagubeni ot sluh, da ne dojde do ograni~u vawa vo znaewata, komunikaciete, dvi`eweto i socijalnadi menzija na negovoto `iveewe. Na liceto so o{ teten sluh treba da mu se ovozm`i da se ~uvstvuvakako vreden i sposoben ~len na op{ testvoto i svoite duhovni i rabotni sposobnosti da gi stavi na raspolagawe na zaednicata. Va`na e i podgotvkata na sredi nata koja treba da poka`e soodvetno razbi rawe neophodno vo procesot na rehabili taci jata. Gluvosta pretstavuva seriozna invalidnost vo odnos na jazi kot, govorot, socijalni ot razvoj i razvojt na li~nosta. Lu|eto vo neкои rabotni sredi ni, vo koi ima vraboteno gluvi rabotnici, dobrovolno ne se pri f}aat da go nau~at gestikulacioti ot govor i ra~nata azbuka na gluvite. No, postojat i poi nakvi iskustva, vo neкои insti tucii bile organi zirani kursevi za izu~uvawe na gestikulacioti ot govor i ra~nata azbuka, a odyi vot bil mlogu golem. Toa e mo{ ne zna~en socijalen fenomen { to zboruva deka kaj lu|eto treba da se razviva ~uvstvoto za pristap kon licata so psihosomatski o{ tetuvawa. Socijalni ot rabotnik { to se gri`i za liceto so te{ki rastrojstva na sluhot zadol`itelno treba da go znae gestikulati vni ot govor zaradi neposredna komunikacija. Na takov na~in se javuva doverba me|u socijalni ot rabotnik i gluvotolice i }e se razdi plat "tajni #koi gluvotolice ve~no }e gi zadr`i vo sebe, ili "modificirano# }e gi soop{ tuva pred drugite preku "tolkuva~#.

Human life is based on relationships dependent on communication, people and social environment. People as social beings realize the entire communication through speech. Deaf people due to hearing loss are unable to learn the speech spontaneously, complex problems in the process of their training and socialization occur. Measures and activities in order to alleviate and compensate the consequences of lost hearing have to be undertaken which will enable knowledge, communication, movement and social dimension in their lives. People with impaired hearing should be enabled to feel as important and capable members of society and put their mental and working abilities on disposal of the community. The readiness of the environment to show appropriate understanding is necessary in the process of rehabilitation. Deafness is a serious disability in relation to language, speech, social and personal development. People in some working environments with deaf employees do not voluntarily accept to learn the language of deaf and their signs. However, there are different experiences. In some institutions, courses for learning the language of deaf and their signs were organized and the interest was big. That is very important social phenomenon, which shows that a feeling for approach to people with psychosomatic impairments should be developed. The social worker who takes care of people with severe hearing impairments should know the language of deaf for direct communication. In such way, a confidence between social worker and deaf person appears and "secrets" will be told which the deaf people keep for themselves for ever or "modified" they will be delivered to others with the help of "interpreter".

Mentalna retardacija predstavuje insuficijencija na op{tite intelektualni sposobnosti koja negativno se odrazuje vrz u-eweto, emocionalna pri sposobnost, adaptacijata vo socijalnata sredina, sposobnostite za koristewe iskustva. Zadol`itelni te pridru`ni manifestacii na mentalna retardacija se socijalnata i nadekvatnost, namaleni mo`nosti za ekonomska samostojnost bez pomo{ na op{testvoto. Mentalna retardacija se klasificira vo ~etiri stepeni i toa: lesna, umerena, te{ka i najte{ka i spored toa socijalnata integracija mo`e da ima razli~ni nivoa vo rehabilitacioni ot tretman. Socijalnata rabota obezbeduvarano otkrivawe, klasifikacija, objektivno informirawe za ni vnata i dni na, obezbeduvaroodveten tretman na licata i ni vnite semejstva, ni vnite prava i uslugi od nematerijalna priroda. Mnogumi na od ovi e lica ostanuvaat delumno ili celosnozavisni od op{testvenite odnosi, od kulturni ot i socijalni ot status na lu|eto od neposrednata okolina.

Vo slo`eniot kompleks na specifi~nite potrebi na telesno invalidnite lica }e go spomneme pra{aweto za sovladuwawe arhitektonski bariere { to gi nametnuva tehni~ko-tehnolo{ki ot razvoj. Treba da se vodi borba za ni vno elimini rawe za da vakvite lu|e ne gi pravi bespomocni vo ostvaruwawe na ni vnite egzistencijalni i kulturni potrebi. Treba da se vodi gri`a i za potrebata od tehni~ki pomagala za transport i komunikacija. Neposrednata fizi~ka pomo{ { to na ovi e lica im ja davaat roditel ite, rodninit e, prijatel ite, gra|anite i socijalni ot rabotnik e zaradi informiranosta za ni vnite specifi~ni potrebi. Psihi~kata optovarenost na vakvite lica bara i soodveten timski tretman, i toa ne samo od socijalnata rabota, tuku i od zdravstvenata za{titata vo razre{uwawe na ni vnite li~ni problemi i probleme te na ni vnite semejstva.

Mental retardation is insufficiency of common intellectual abilities that has negative influence on learning, emotional adaptation, adaptation in social environment, abilities for using experiences. Required side effects of mental retardation are social inadequacy, reduced abilities for economic independence without assistance of the society. There is a four-degree classification of mental retardation: easy, moderate, hard and severe. Different levels of rehabilitation treatment are possible according to social integration. Social work provides early detection, classification, objective information on their future, appropriate treatment of people and their families, their rights and services of immaterial nature. Most of these people stay dependent partially or completely on social relationship, cultural and social status of people in their environment.

In the complex of specific needs of physically disabled people, the issue of surmounting architectonic barriers imposed by technological development will be mentioned here. They have to be eliminated, so these people do not feel helpless in their existential and cultural needs. Care should be taken for technical aids for transport and communication. Direct physical assistance given to these people by parents, relatives, friends, citizens and social workers is due to the information on their specific needs. The psychic burden of these people requires appropriate team work, not only of social work, but health care in solving their personal problems as well as the problems of their families.

2. Eti~ki aspekti na socijalna rabota vo ostvaruvawe na op{ testvenata gri`a za licata so invalidnost

Motivite za izbor na socijalna rabota od aspekt na trajno profesionalno anga`irawe, vo stru~nata literatura posebno ne se eksplicirani. Ova prawe, so svoje socijalni, psiholo{ki, op{ testveni i drugi implikacii ima {i rok domen za rasprava, no, }e se zadr`ime samo na odredeni impresii od dosega{ nata organizirana socijalna rabota vo zemjawa. Ne postojat dovolno istra`uvawa i stru~ni prilozii od oblata na etikata i socijalna rabota {to vo sega{ ni ve op{ testveno-ekonomski transformacii sé pove}e od potrebni.

Opredelbata za socijalna rabota pretstavuva epiloga na sopstvenite streme`i za samodoka`uvawe. No, ne samo kako filantropsko eksponirawe, tuku i kako vizija za edna sovest raspnata me|u protivre~nosti (dobrina i zlo, izobilstvo i nema{tina, ~ove~nost i ne~ove~nost, zdravje i bolest, ra|awe i smrt, mladost i starost, tradicionalno i moderno, konzervativno i progresivno, vojna i mir, maka i radost, `elbi i mo`nosti, i dividualno i op{ testveno, svi repost i krotkost, prgavost i mrzelivost, intimnost i otvorenost, skromnost i arogancija i tn.) {to go naru{uvaat totalitetot na sovr{enstvo, ostavaj}i prostor za postojana borba kako civilizacijska tendencija na poedinec ot op{ testvoto.

Da se po~ituva i da se ceni ~ovekovata li~nost e osnova na odnositelno sekoe op{ testvo, atri but na gra|ani not i negovata egzistencija vo sferata na etikata, semejstvoto i sosejstvoto. Op{ testvoto vo svojot razvoj i demokratizacija se orientira kon povrzuvawe na lu|eto, dr`avite, narodite, zaedni~ki da re{avaat bitni prawe za li~nata sudbina i za sudbinata na svetot vo celost. Takvata konstelacija go motivira poedinec ot socijalna rabota kako `ivotna opredelba, potreba i `elba da i pomogne na sekoja i dividual

2. Ethical aspects of social work in implementation of social care for disabled people

The motives for social work choice from the aspect of permanent professional engagement have not been explicit in professional literature. This issue with its social, psychological and other implications has a wide range of discussion, but we shall point out certain impressions from experiences of organized social work in our country. There are not enough researches and professional articles in the field of ethics and social work, which are more than necessary in present socio-economic transformations. Determination for social work is an epilogue of ones' own desires for proving themselves. It is not only a philanthropic exposition, on the contrary, a vision of conscience that is torn by contradictories. Good and evil, abundance and poverty, human and inhuman, health and disease, birth and death, youth and old age, traditional and modern, conservative and progressive, war and peace, trouble and joy, desires and possibilities, individual and social, cruelty and gentleness, grumpy and lazy, intimacy and openness, modesty and arrogance. They all disturb the totality of perfection, leaving a space for permanent struggle as civilization tendency between individual and society.

Basis for society relationships, characteristic of people and their existence in the sphere of ethics, family and environment is to respect and value human personality. The society in its development and democratization orients itself towards joining people, countries and nationalities in order to solve essential issues of personal fate and world as a whole. Such constellation motivates the individual for social work as life profession, need and desire to help individuals

individua za da gi u`iva blagodeti te na progresot, a u{ te pove}e ako pomo{ ta e nemi novna.

@el bata da se pomaga, da se pravi dobro, da se drugaruva, da se sprijateluva da se sorabotuva, e uslovena obi~ajna norma, koja po nepi{ an zakon inspirira i vr{ i vlijanie vrz sevkupnoto dejstvuvawe na li~nosta. Toa kaj nas, sé u{ te, pretstavuva nacionalen beleg i skapoceno nasledstvo koe emoti vno obedi nuva generaci i. Gostopri mstvoto pak, kako osobenost na na{ i ot narod, poznato e { i rum svetot i pretstavuva izvor na ~ove{ tina, streme` za solidarnost. Mo` e da se zaklu~i deka opredelbata za socijalna rabota e uslovena od tradicijata i od op{ testvenite odnosi vo ~ie sredi { te e me|usebnoto po~i tuvawe.

2.1. Principi na socijalna rabota vo ost varuvawe za{ titata na licata so invalidnost

Socijalnata rabota spored svojata su{ tina poa|a od interesite na gra|anite i obrvski te na op{ testvenata zaednica da im ovozmoe i pomo{ na onie { to imaat potreba. Taa pomo{ ne e somilost tuku obezbeduvawe materijalna i socijalna sigurnost na gra|anite zaradi sozdavawe zaedni~ka blagosostojba na dr` avata i poedi necot.

Principite na socijalnata rabota vo tretmanot, za{ titata na licata so invalidnost, sodr` at odredeni specifi~nosti vo zavisnost od vidot i stepenot na psihosomatski te o{ tetuvawa.

Pozna~ajni principi na socijalnata rabota vo sevkupni ot tretman na licata so invalidnost se:

A. Princip na zadol` it elno rano ot -kri vawe, prijavuvawe i regist rirawe, dijagnost icirawe, klasifikacija, evident irawe i upat uvawe na soodvet en t ret man,

to enjoy the benefits of progress, especially when the assistance is unavoidable.

The desire to help, to do good, to be friendly, to make friends, to cooperate is conditioned habitual norm, which inspires and has influence on complete individual activity. It is still our national characteristic and precious heritage, which emotionally has united generations. The hospitality, as a characteristic of our people is known all over the world and is a source of humanity, a desire for solidarity. We can conclude that the determination for social work is conditioned by tradition and social relationships focused on mutual respect.

2.1. Principles of social work in implementation of care for disabled people

Social work, according to its essence, starts from people's interest and obligations of social community to provide assistance to those who need it. That assistance is not compassion, but it is a material and social security of people in order to create mutual welfare of state and individuals.

The principles of social work in treatment, care of people disabilities have certain specifics dependant on type and level of psychosomatic impairments.

Important principles in social work in treatment of people with disabilities are:

A. Principle of compulsory early detection, reporting and registering, diagnosis, classification, evidence and referring to appropriate treatment,

B. Princip na celosno, objektivno in stvarno informiranje za sostojte na licata, možnost, prognoze, probleme in potrebe od angažman na sejmestvo in sodvetni instituciji,

V. Princip na toleranca, prijazne povzemanje na ljubeznost,

G. Princip na efikasnost in racionalnost v opredeljevanju in sproževanju tona tretjih, meril in prava,

D. Princip na koordinacijo in sodelovanje organizacij, socialno-humanitarnih organizacij, ustanov in služb, ki se vključijo v proces na začetku in rehabilitacijo,

\\ Princip na kontinuiteto na socialnata dela v odkritju, klasifikacijo, rehabilitacijo in socialno integracijo,

E. Princip na pripravo na sredstva, ki jih imajo ljudje zaradi njihove prijazne komunikacije, udeležbo v kulturno-zabavni in športni rekreaciji.

Namest o zaključku

Egzistencialna ljubeznost in invalidnost povzročata zadovoljevanje njihove življenjske potrebe in potrebe na življenjskem mestu. Se nametno potreba od kontinuirano sledenje in analize na probleme, ki so posledica invalidnosti psihosomatski očitava. Zaradi ekonomske krize in z objektivni in subjektivni razlogi, ljubeznost in invalidnost se pojavljata v neprijetnih okoliščinah. Socialna dela mora se reševati osnovne egzistencialne probleme, probleme na življenjskem mestu in sodelovanja, ki so posledica ljubeznosti. Predmet socialne dela je bitnost in konfliktna delovna mesta, razvodi, alkoholizem, kockanje, asocialno odnesovanje, ki se reševati kontinuirano so vzpostavljeni sistem na davne usluge v vidu socialne dela.

B. Principle of complete, objective and professional information on conditions of people, possibilities, anticipations, problems and needs of family and relevant institution engagements,

C. Principle of tolerance, acceptance and respect of people,

D. Principle of efficiency and rationality in determination and realization of treatment, measures and rights,

E. Principle of coordination and cooperation with organs, socio-humanitarian organizations, institutions and services included in the process of care and rehabilitation,

F. Principle of continuity of social work with detection, classification, rehabilitation and social integration,

G. Principle of preparation of community, where such people live and work, for their acceptance, communication, participation in cultural, entertaining, sport and recreation life.

Instead of conclusion

The existence of people with disabilities is connected with satisfaction of their life needs and the needs of their families. The need for continuous follow up and analysis of problems, which are results of their psychosomatic disability, is imposed. Due to economic crisis and objective and subjective reasons, people with disabilities live in unpleasant conditions. Social work has to solve basic existential problems, problems of their families and families these people will raise. Social work faces frequent conflicts at work places, divorces, alcoholism, gambling and asocial behavior and solves them continuously with established system of providing services.

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